

Under a False Moon: The Rise of Space-Based Light Pollution

Miles Timpe¹

DOI:

Abstract: For billions of years, the celestial sphere has acted as a universal clock and reliable map for life on Earth. As a result, many species have evolved to regulate critical biological, physiological, and behavioral functions by the regular cycles of sunlight, moonlight, and starlight and navigate by recognizable patterns in the sky. These celestial patterns and photocycles are so fundamentally intertwined with life that many species have come to depend on them at a molecular level. Similarly, the use and importance of these celestial signals is widespread across human cultures. Accelerating human activity in space has the potential to significantly disrupt the natural patterns and cycles that characterize Earth's celestial sphere. This is not a hypothetical or distant problem, as rapidly decreasing launch costs and accelerating technological innovation are opening outer space to an increasingly diverse array of human activity—including plans to display advertising, art, and other messages from low Earth orbit, as well as space-based climate engineering projects which seek to provide widespread nighttime illumination and solar power from orbit. Thus, the rapid commercialization of space and lack of regulatory clarity present an urgent need for comprehensive technical, ethical, and regulatory frameworks, particularly for those spaceflight activities most likely to be realized in the coming years. This presentation will explore current and proposed space missions which risk introducing significant light pollution into the celestial sphere and their connections on Earth's biosphere and human cultures.

Keywords: astrobiology; spaceflight; earth-space system; anthropocene; photoecology.

Corresponding Author: mtimpe@ethz.ch

¹ Collegium Helveticum, ETH Zürich, Switzerland